

**COMPARATIVE RESEARCH OF INDIRECT OBJECT IN THE ENGLISH
AND UZBEK LANGUAGES**

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Abstract. This article provides information on analyzing the indirect object in English and comparing it in Uzbek sentence, comparison, syntax, Uzbek and English language.

Key words. Sentence, comparison, syntax, Uzbek and English language.

Introduction.

Etiquette is a clearly visible relationship of moral culture as one of the manifestations of the external culture of a person, mutual behavior in relationships governs the implementation of rules.

In fact, the concept of "etiquette" dates back to 2.5 - 3 thousand years BC in ancient Egypt appeared. The term "etiquette" appeared at the end of the 17th century. But the ancient sources of etiquette rules are in the form of customs, pictures and customs proves that it existed in the tribes since ancient times. Such not fulfilling the rules completely with betrayal of the community or tribe in which he lives was equal. At first, such rules are not only moral, but also legal, economic, it also included religious and blood-kinship relations. Each of the team one member obeyed him unconditionally. Thus, the rules of etiquette in this period are independent did not have, it was implemented mainly depending on the social problems of the community. In other words, these rules were created at the request

of the natural community. Such requirements execution was supervised by elders of the tribe or community.

Main part.

Comparative typology is a branch of linguistics comparing languages in order to establish their similarities and differences. Its object is not singular and individual cases of similarity and difference but those which are common for large groups of language elements. Comparative typology classifies languages according to their structure. Although languages may differ in their material (i.e. have no words of the same root, or common morphemes) their structure (i.e. relations between the elements, functions of the elements) may be similar.

English – Indo European Family – Germanic – Analytic – SVO

Uzbek – Turkic family – Southeastern – Uighur-chagatay – Agglutinative – SOV

Uzbek U xonani tozalayotgan edi (Verb-final language)

 He/she [subject] the room-[Object]+[Acc] tidying up [Past continuous] was [auxiliary verb]

English “She was tidying up the room” (Verb-initial language)

(Nouns marked for case + Verbs marked for tense)

Uzbek U qalamni sindirdi (SOV)

 He [subject] the pen-[Object]+[Acc] broke [past]

English “He broke the pen” (SVO)

(Nouns marked for case + Verbs marked for tense).

Indirect objects can be either an individual noun or a noun phrase.

I loaned him some money.

In this example, him is the indirect object because he receives the money (the direct object). But what if we got a little more descriptive . . .

I loaned my tall, bald friend of ten years some money.

Let’s outline a few more examples. We’ll put the *direct objects* in italics and the **indirect objects** in bold:

Becky baked **Bernice** a *plateful* of *cookies*.

(Becky baked what? A plateful of cookies. Who received the cookies? Bernice.)

Her mom brought **her** a *glassful* of *seashells*.

(Her mom brought what? A glassful of seashells. Who received the glassful of seashells? Her.)

In art class, I made **my roommate** a *sculpture*.

(I made what? A sculpture. Who received it? My roommate.)

Marcia gave **her sister** a *sidelong stare*.

(Marcia gave what? A sidelong stare. Who received it? Her sister.)

Can we tell **our friends** *the story of how we met?*

(We're telling what? The story of how we met. Who's going to hear the story? Our friends.)

The sun gave **the garden** a *pocketful of sunshine*.

(The sun gave what? A pocketful of sunshine. Who received it? The garden.)

In this case, the indirect object is the entire phrase my tall, bald friend of ten years.

Translation is the art of re-creation, a high artistic creation, even if it is a creation various materials that require research, work, and patience from the translator. It is a creation that requires hard work. The concept of translation meaning is very broad, because "What is translation?" to the question of representatives of various fields they answer differently. A person translates a book written in one language into another language. When someone says to turn, another person interprets the idea expressed in one language in another language he knows that it consists of explaining to the speakers. A third person and in his opinion, movies are also translated, so translation is acting in one language means to translate the speech of the acting actor into the second, third, etc. languages.

Approaching the translation from the point of view of linguistic translation studies, the definition is as follows can be given: Translation, which is a complex form of human activity, is in one language preserving the created speech expression (text), its unity of form and content, is a creative process of re-creation based on the

means of a foreign language. So, the truth a speech expression created with the help of language tools belonging to the translation language is replaced by such an expression created on the basis of laws. That's 8 in this way, the substantive and stylistic adequacy of the texts in the original and translated languages is created is brought.

Syntax is a part of grammar that examines word combinations and sentences, the basis of which is the doctrine of sentences: sentence construction, rules of joining words, sentence structure, function, use, interrelation of sentences, etc. . Syntax is inextricably linked with other branches of linguistics. For example, morphology studies the structure of words, while syntax examines their connection, connection, ways and means of joining. The word is also studied in the lexicon as a lexical unit, but its real meaning is determined in the sentence. At the same time, tone is important in the formation of a sentence, which shows the dependence of syntax on the phonetic system.

In Uzbek, the order of words in a sentence is mostly free. Changing the place of words does not seriously affect their grammatical status. However, this affects the content and methodical aspect of the sentence.

Let's compare: I met Ghalib in the market.

I met the winner in the market.

I met Ghalib in the market.

In these sentences, the unique logic accent of the Uzbek language is used. In the first sentence, I met Ghalib, not someone else, and in the second sentence, I met him in the market, not somewhere else and in the third sentence, the meaning of what I met, not someone else, is expressed. In Uzbek, the word with logic accent is usually placed before the participle. When the logical stress falls on a participle, it does not change the place of the participle, but it is said in its place with a high tone.

Conclusion.

In fact, at the time when all the conditions for the spiritual development of our people are being created in our country, the science of linguistics should also serve

this purpose. Our national linguistics, which has chosen the path of independent development, is currently on the way to determine the place of language in human social activity, researching its communicative nature and anthropocentric features, while adopting the advanced ideas characteristic of world linguistics.

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